
Whitening for Self-Supervised Representation Learning

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Abstract

Most of the current self-supervised representation learning (SSL) methods are based on the *contrastive loss* and the instance-discrimination task, where augmented versions of the same image instance (“positives”) are contrasted with instances extracted from other images (“negatives”). For the learning to be effective, many negatives should be compared with a positive pair, which is computationally demanding. In this paper, we propose a different direction and a new loss function for SSL, which is based on the *whitening* of the latent-space features. The whitening operation has a “scattering” effect on the batch samples, avoiding degenerate solutions where all the sample representations collapse to a single point. Our solution does not require asymmetric networks and it is conceptually simple. Moreover, since negatives are not needed, we can extract multiple positive pairs from the same image instance. The source code of the method and of all the experiments is available at: <https://github.com/htdt/self-supervised>.

1. Introduction

One of the current main bottlenecks in deep network training is the dependence on large annotated training datasets, and this motivates the recent surge of interest in unsupervised methods. Specifically, in self-supervised representation learning (SSL), a network is (pre-)trained without any form of manual annotation, thus providing a means to extract information from unlabeled-data sources (e.g., text corpora, videos, images from the Internet, etc.). In self-supervision, label-based information is replaced by a prediction problem using some form of *context* or using a *pretext* task. Pioneering work in this direction was done in Natural Language Processing (NLP), in which the co-occurrence

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of words in a sentence is used to learn a language model (Mikolov et al., 2013a;b; Devlin et al., 2019). In Computer Vision, typical contexts or pretext tasks are based on: (1) the temporal consistency in videos (Wang & Gupta, 2015; Misra et al., 2016; Dwibedi et al., 2019), (2) the spatial order of patches in still images (Noroozi & Favaro, 2016; Misra & van der Maaten, 2020; Hénaff et al., 2019) or (3) simple image transformation techniques (Ji et al., 2019; He et al., 2020; Wu et al., 2018). The intuitive idea behind most of these methods is to collect pairs of *positive* and *negative* samples: two positive samples should share the same semantics, while negatives should be perceptually different. A triplet loss (Sohn, 2016; Schroff et al., 2015; Hermans et al., 2017; Wang & Gupta, 2015; Misra et al., 2016) can then be used to learn a metric space representing the human perceptual similarity. However, most of the recent studies use a contrastive loss (Hadsell et al., 2006) or one of its variants (Gutmann & Hyvärinen, 2010; van den Oord et al., 2018; Hjelm et al., 2019), while Tschannen et al. (2019) show the relation between the triplet and the contrastive losses.

It is worth noticing that the success of both kinds of losses is strongly affected by the number and the quality of the negative samples. For instance, in the case of the triplet loss, a common practice is to select *hard/semi-hard* negatives (Schroff et al., 2015; Hermans et al., 2017). On the other hand, Hjelm et al. (2019) have shown that the contrastive loss needs a large number of negatives to be competitive. This implies using batches with a large size, which is computationally demanding, especially with high-resolution images. In order to alleviate this problem, Wu et al. (2018) use a *memory bank* of negatives, which is composed of feature-vector representations of all the training samples. He et al. (2020) conjecture that the use of large and fixed-representation vocabularies is one of the keys to the success of self-supervision in NLP. The solution proposed in MoCo He et al. (2020) extends Wu et al. (2018) using a memory-efficient queue of the last visited negatives, together with a *momentum encoder* which preserves the intra-queue representation consistency. Chen et al. (2020a) have performed large-scale experiments confirming that a large number of negatives (and therefore a large batch size) is required for the contrastive loss to be efficient.

Very recently, Grill et al. (2020) proposed an alternative

direction, in which only positives are used, together with two networks, where the *online* network tries to predict the representation of a positive extracted by the *target* network. Despite the large success of BYOL (Grill et al., 2020), the reason why the two networks can avoid a collapsed representation (e.g., where all the images are mapped to the same point) is still unclear (Fetterman & Albrecht, 2020; Tian et al., 2020b; Chen & He, 2020; Richemond et al., 2020). According to (Fetterman & Albrecht, 2020; Tian et al., 2020b), one of the important ingredients which is *implicitly* used in BYOL to avoid degenerate solutions, is the use of the Batch Norm (BN) (Ioffe & Szegedy, 2015) in the projection/prediction heads (see Sec. 3.1). In this paper we propose to generalize this finding and we show that, using a full *whitening* of the latent space features is *sufficient* to avoid collapsed representations, without the need of additional momentum networks (Grill et al., 2020), siamese networks with stop-gradient operations (Chen & He, 2020) or the use of specific, batch-based optimizers like LARS (You et al., 2017; Fetterman & Albrecht, 2020).

In more detail, we propose a new SSL loss function, which first *scatters* all the sample representations in a spherical distribution¹ and then *penalizes* the positive pairs which are far from each other. Specifically, given a set of samples $V = \{\mathbf{v}_i\}$, corresponding to the current mini-batch of images $B = \{x_i\}$, we first project the elements of V onto a spherical distribution using a *whitening* transform (Siarohin et al., 2019). The whitened representations $\{\mathbf{z}_i\}$, corresponding to V , are normalized and then used to compute a Mean Squared Error (MSE) loss which accumulates the error considering only positive pairs $(\mathbf{z}_i, \mathbf{z}_j)$. To avoid a representation collapse, we do not need to *contrast* positives against negatives as in the contrastive loss or in the triplet loss because the optimization process leads to shrinking the distance between positive pairs and, indirectly, scatters the other samples to satisfy the overall spherical-distribution constraint.

In summary, our contributions are the following:

- We propose a new SSL loss function, Whitening MSE (W-MSE). W-MSE constrains the batch samples to lie in a spherical distribution and it is an alternative to positive-negative instance contrasting methods.
- Our loss does not need a large number of negatives, thus we can include more positives in the current batch. We indeed demonstrate that multiple positive pairs extracted from one image improve the performance.
- We empirically show that our W-MSE loss outperforms the commonly adopted contrastive loss and it is com-

¹Here and in the following, with “spherical distribution” we mean a distribution with a zero-mean and an identity-matrix covariance.

petitive with respect to state-of-the-art SSL methods like (Grill et al., 2020; Chen & He, 2020).

2. Background and Related Work

A typical SSL method is composed of two main components: a *pretext task*, which exploits some a-priori knowledge about the domain to automatically extract supervision from data, and a *loss function*. In this section we briefly review both aspects, and we additionally analyse the recent literature concerning feature whitening.

Pretext tasks. The temporal consistency in a video provides an intuitive form of self-supervision: temporally-close frames usually contain a similar semantic content (Wang & Gupta, 2015; van den Oord et al., 2018). Misra et al. (2016) extended this idea using the relative temporal order of 3 frames, while Dwivedi et al. (2019) used a *temporal cycle consistency* for self-supervision, which is based on comparing two videos sharing the same semantics and computing inter-video frame-to-frame nearest neighbour assignments.

When dealing with still images, the most common pretext task is *instance discrimination* (Wu et al. (2018)): from a training image x , a composition of data-augmentation techniques are used to extract two different views of x (x_i and x_j). Commonly adopted transformations are: image cropping, rotation, color jittering, Sobel filtering, etc. The learner, which is usually composed of an encoder and a projection head, is then required to discriminate (x_i, x_j) from other views extracted from other samples (Wu et al., 2018; Ji et al., 2019; He et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2020a).

Denosing auto-encoders (Vincent et al., 2008) add random noise to the input image and try to recover the original image. Xu et al. (2020) enforce consistency across different image resolutions. More sophisticated pretext tasks consist in predicting the spatial order of image patches (Noroozi & Favaro, 2016; Misra & van der Maaten, 2020) or in reconstructing large masked regions of the image (Pathak et al., 2016). Hjelm et al. (2019); Bachman et al. (2019) compare the holistic representation of an input image with a patch of the same image. Hénaff et al. (2019) use a similar idea, where the comparison depends on the patch order: the appearance of a given patch should be predicted given the appearance of the patches which lie above it in the image.

We use standard data augmentations (Chen et al., 2020a) to get positive pairs, which is a simple solution and does not require a pretext-task specific network architecture (Hjelm et al., 2019; Bachman et al., 2019; Hénaff et al., 2019).

Loss functions. Denosing auto-encoders use a *reconstruction loss* which compares the generated image with the input image before adding noise. Other generative methods use an *adversarial loss* in which a discriminator provides supervisory information to the generator (Donahue et al., 2017;

Donahue & Simonyan, 2019).

Early SSL (deep) discriminative methods used a *triplet loss* (Wang & Gupta, 2015; Misra et al., 2016): given two *positive* images x_i, x_j and a *negative* x_k (Sec. 1), together with their corresponding latent-space representations $\mathbf{z}_i, \mathbf{z}_j, \mathbf{z}_k$, this loss penalizes those cases in which \mathbf{z}_i and \mathbf{z}_k are closer to each other than \mathbf{z}_i and \mathbf{z}_j plus a margin m :

$$L_{Triplet} = -\max(\mathbf{z}_i^T \mathbf{z}_k - \mathbf{z}_i^T \mathbf{z}_j + m, 0). \quad (1)$$

Most of the recent SSL discriminative methods are based on some *contrastive loss* (Hadsell et al., 2006) variant, in which \mathbf{z}_i and \mathbf{z}_j are contrasted against a set of negative pairs. Following the common formulation proposed by van den Oord et al. (2018), the contrastive loss is given by:

$$L_{Contrastive} = -\log \frac{\exp(\mathbf{z}_i^T \mathbf{z}_j / \tau)}{\sum_{k=1, k \neq i}^K \exp(\mathbf{z}_i^T \mathbf{z}_k / \tau)}, \quad (2)$$

where τ is a *temperature* hyperparameter which should be manually set and the sum in the denominator is over a set of $K - 1$ negative samples. Usually K is the size of the current batch, i.e., $K = 2N$, being N the number of positive pairs. However, as shown by Hjelm et al. (2019), the contrastive loss (2) requires a large number of negative samples to be competitive. Wu et al. (2018); He et al. (2020) use a set of negatives much larger than the current batch, by pre-computing representations of old samples. SimCLR (Chen et al., 2020a) uses a simpler, but computationally very demanding, solution based on large batches.

Tschannen et al. (2019) show that the success of the contrastive loss is likely related to learning a metric space, similarly to what happens with a triplet loss, while Wang & Isola (2020) investigate the uniformity and the alignment properties of the L_2 normalized contrastive loss. In the same paper, the authors propose two new losses ($\mathcal{L}_{\text{uniform}}$ and $\mathcal{L}_{\text{align}}$) which explicitly optimize these characteristics.

In BYOL (Grill et al. (2020)), given a pair of positives (x_i, x_j) , x_i is fed to the “online” network, which should predict the output of the “target” network, where the latter receives x_j as input and its parameters are a running average of the former. Concurrently with our work, Chen & He (2020) have simplified this scheme, introducing SimSiam, where both samples x_i and x_j are encoded using the same network (i.e., a Siamese architecture with a shared encoder). Both BYOL and SimSiam include an additional asymmetric prediction head to compare the latent representations of x_i and x_j , a stop-gradient operation with respect to the element of the positive pair not used by the prediction head, and an MSE loss of the L_2 -normalized latent representations. In these methods, both the projection and the prediction head

include BN. Chen & He (2020) show that these BN layers are a crucial component of SimSiam, and their removal results in a dramatic performance degradation. Fetterman & Albrecht (2020) and Tian et al. (2020b) have empirically confirmed the importance of BN in BYOL, and they show that BN allows BYOL to avoid collapsing the representation of all images to a constant value, which would make the MSE computation equal to zero. Our work can be seen as a generalization of this finding *with a much simpler network architecture* and without the need to rely on asymmetric learning protocols (see Sec. 3.1). Moreover, our loss formulation is simpler also because it does not require a proper setting of hyperparameters such as τ in Eq. 2 or m in Eq. 1.

Finally, another recent line of work is based on clustering approaches (Bautista et al., 2016; Caron et al., 2018; Zhuang et al., 2019). For instance, SwAV (Caron et al., 2020) computes a cross-entropy loss over the image-to-cluster prototype assignments, and it is one of the state-of-the-art SSL methods. One of the ingredients of SwAV is the use of multiple positives, and in Sec. 3.1 we show that our proposal can exploit multiple crops in a more efficient way.

Feature whitening. We adopt the efficient and stable Cholesky decomposition (Dereniowski & Marek, 2004) based *whitening* transform proposed by Siarohin et al. (2019) to project our latent-space vectors into a spherical distribution (see Sec. 3). Note that Huang et al. (2018); Siarohin et al. (2019) use whitening transforms in the intermediate layers of the network for a completely different task: extending BN to a multivariate batch normalization.

3. The Whitening MSE Loss

Given an image x , we extract an embedding $\mathbf{z} = f(x; \theta)$ using an encoder network $f(\cdot; \theta)$ parametrized with θ (more details below). We require that: (1) the image embeddings are drawn from a non-degenerate distribution (the latter being a distribution where, e.g., all the representations collapse to a single point), and (2) positive image pairs (x_i, x_j) , which share a similar semantics, should be clustered close to each other. We formulate this problem as follows:

$$\min_{\theta} \mathbb{E}[dist(\mathbf{z}_i, \mathbf{z}_j)], \quad (3)$$

$$s.t. cov(\mathbf{z}_i, \mathbf{z}_i) = cov(\mathbf{z}_j, \mathbf{z}_j) = I, \quad (4)$$

where $dist(\cdot)$ is a distance between vectors, I is the identity matrix and $(\mathbf{z}_i, \mathbf{z}_j)$ corresponds to a positive pair of images (x_i, x_j) . With Eq. 4, we constrain the distribution of the \mathbf{z} values to be non-degenerate, hence avoiding that all the probability mass is concentrated in a single point. Moreover, Eq. 4 makes all the components of \mathbf{z} to be linearly independent from each other, which encourages the different dimensions of \mathbf{z} to represent different semantic content. We

Figure 1. A schematic representation of the W-MSE based optimization process. Positive pairs are indicated with the same shapes and colors. (1) A representation of the batch features in V when training starts. (2, 3) The distribution of the elements after whitening and the L_2 normalization. (4) The MSE computed over the normalized \mathbf{z} features encourages the network to move the positive pair representations closer to each other. (5) The subsequent iterations move closer and closer the positive pairs, while the relative layout of the other samples is forced to lie in a spherical distribution.

define the distance with the cosine similarity, implemented with MSE between normalized vectors:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{dist}(\mathbf{z}_i, \mathbf{z}_j) &= \left\| \frac{\mathbf{z}_i}{\|\mathbf{z}_i\|_2} - \frac{\mathbf{z}_j}{\|\mathbf{z}_j\|_2} \right\|_2^2 \\ &= 2 - 2 \frac{\langle \mathbf{z}_i, \mathbf{z}_j \rangle}{\|\mathbf{z}_i\|_2 \cdot \|\mathbf{z}_j\|_2} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

In the Supplementary Material we also include other experiments in which the cosine similarity is replaced by the Euclidean distance. We provide below the details on how positive image samples are collected, how they are encoded and how the above optimization is implemented.

First, similarly to Chen et al. (2020a), we obtain positive samples sharing the same semantics from a single image x and using standard image transformation techniques. Specifically, we use a composition of image cropping, grayscaling and color jittering transformations $T(\cdot; \mathbf{p})$. The parameters (\mathbf{p}) are selected uniformly at random and independently for each positive sample extracted from the same image: $x_i = T(x; \mathbf{p}_i)$. We concisely indicate with $\text{pos}(i, j)$ the fact that x_i and x_j ($x_i, x_j \in B$, B the current batch) have been extracted from the same image.

The number of positive samples per image d may vary, trading off diversity in the batch and the amount of the training

signal. Favoring more negatives, most of the methods use only one positive pair ($d = 2$). However, Ji et al. (2019) have demonstrated improved performance with 5 samples, while Caron et al. (2020) use 8 samples. In our MSE-based loss (see below), we use all the possible $d(d-1)/2$ combinations of positive samples. We include experiments for $d = 2$ (1 positive pair) and $d = 4$ (6 positive pairs). Note that our implementation includes *batch slicing* (described below), where the choice of d is related with the sub-batch size, and larger d values can produce instability issues.

For representation learning, we use a backbone *encoder* network $E(\cdot)$. $E(\cdot)$, trained without human supervision, will be used in Sec. 4 for evaluation using standard protocols. We use a standard ResNet (He et al., 2016) as the encoder, and $\mathbf{h} = E(x)$ is the output of the average-pooling layer. This choice has the advantage to be simple and easily reproducible, in contrast to other methods which use encoder architectures specific for a given pretext task (see Sec. 2). Since $\mathbf{h} \in \mathbb{R}^{512}$ or $\mathbf{h} \in \mathbb{R}^{2048}$ is a high-dimensional vector, following Chen et al. (2020a) we use a nonlinear projection head $g(\cdot)$ to project \mathbf{h} in a lower dimensional space: $\mathbf{v} = g(\mathbf{h})$, where $g(\cdot)$ is implemented with a MLP with one hidden layer and a BN layer. The whole network $f(\cdot)$ is given by the composition of $g(\cdot)$ with $E(\cdot)$ (see Fig. 2). Note that we do not use prediction heads like in (Grill et al., 2020; Chen & He, 2020).

Given N original images and a batch of samples $B = \{x_1, \dots, x_K\}$, where $K = Nd$, let $V = \{\mathbf{v}_1, \dots, \mathbf{v}_K\}$, be the corresponding batch of features obtained as described above. In the proposed W-MSE loss, we compute the MSE over all $Nd(d-1)/2$ positive pairs, where constraint 4 is satisfied using the reparameterization of the \mathbf{v} variables with the whitened variables \mathbf{z} :

$$L_{W-MSE}(V) = \frac{2}{Nd(d-1)} \sum \text{dist}(\mathbf{z}_i, \mathbf{z}_j), \quad (6)$$

where the sum is over $(\mathbf{v}_i, \mathbf{v}_j) \in V$, $\text{pos}(i, j) = \text{true}$, $\mathbf{z} = \text{Whitening}(\mathbf{v})$, and:

$$\text{Whitening}(\mathbf{v}) = W_V(\mathbf{v} - \boldsymbol{\mu}_V). \quad (7)$$

In Eq. 7, $\boldsymbol{\mu}_V$ is the mean of the elements in V : $\boldsymbol{\mu}_V = \frac{1}{K} \sum_k \mathbf{v}_k$, while the matrix W_V is such that: $W_V^\top W_V = \Sigma_V^{-1}$, being Σ_V the covariance matrix of V :

$$\Sigma_V = \frac{1}{K-1} \sum_k (\mathbf{v}_k - \boldsymbol{\mu}_V)(\mathbf{v}_k - \boldsymbol{\mu}_V)^\top. \quad (8)$$

For more details on how W_V is computed, we refer to the Supplementary Material. Equation 7 performs the full whitening of each $\mathbf{v}_i \in V$ and the resulting set of vectors

Figure 2. A scheme of our training procedure. First, d ($d = 4$ in this case) positive samples are generated using augmentations. These images are transformed into vectors with the encoder $E(\cdot)$. Next, they are projected onto a lower dimensional space with a projection head $g(\cdot)$. Then, Whitening projects these vectors onto a spherical distribution, optionally followed by an L_2 normalization. Finally, the dashed curves show all the $d(d - 1)/2$ comparisons used in our W-MSE loss.

$Z = \{\mathbf{z}_1, \dots, \mathbf{z}_K\}$ lies in a zero-centered distribution with a covariance matrix equal to the identity matrix (Fig. 1).

The intuition behind the proposed loss is that Eq. 6 penalizes positives which are far apart from each other, thus leading $g(E(\cdot))$ to shrink the inter-positive distances. On the other hand, since Z must lie in a spherical distribution, the other samples should be “moved” and rearranged in order to satisfy constraint 4 (see Fig. 1).

Figure 3. Batch slicing. V is first partitioned in d parts ($d = 2$ in this example). We randomly permute the first part and we apply the same permutation to the other $d - 1$ parts. Then, we further split all the partitions and we create sub-batches (V_i). Each V_i is independently used to compute the sub-batch specific whitening matrix W_V^i and centroid μ_V^i .

Batch slicing. The estimation of the MSE in Eq. 6 depends on the whitening matrix W_V , which may have a high variance over consecutive-iteration batches V_t, V_{t+1}, \dots . For this reason, inspired by the resampling methods (Efron, 1982), given a batch V , we slice V in different non-overlapping sub-batches and we compute a whitening matrix independently for each sub-batch. In more detail, we first partition the batch in d parts, being d the number of positives extracted from one image. In this way, each partition contains elements extracted from different original images (i.e., no

pair of positives is included in a single partition, see Fig. 3). Then, we randomly permute the elements of the each partition, using the same permutation for all the partitions. Next, each partition is further split in sub-batches, using the heuristic that the size of each sub-batch (V_i) should be equal to the size of embedding ($|v|$) times 2 (this prevents instability issues when computing the covariance matrices). For each V_i , we use only its elements to compute a corresponding whitening matrix W_V^i , which is used to whiten the elements of V_i only (Fig. 3). In the loss computation (Eq. 6), all the elements of all the sub-batches are used, thus implicitly alleviating the differences among the different whitening matrices. Finally, it is possible to repeat the whole operation several times and to average the result to get a more robust estimate of Eq. 6. Note that, despite using smaller batches may increase the instability in computing the whitening matrix, this is compensated by having a different W_V^i for each V_i , and by the possibility to iterate the sampling process with different permutations for the same V .

3.1. Discussion

In a common *instance-discrimination* task (Sec. 2), e.g., solved using Eq. 2, the similarity of a positive pair ($\mathbf{z}_i^T \mathbf{z}_j$) is contrasted with the similarity computed with respect to all the other samples (\mathbf{z}_k) in the batch ($\mathbf{z}_i^T \mathbf{z}_k, 1 \leq k \leq K, k \neq i$). However, \mathbf{z}_k and \mathbf{z}_i , extracted from different image instances, can occasionally share the same semantics (e.g., x_i and x_k are two different image *instances* of the unknown “cat” *class*). Conversely, the proposed W-MSE loss does not force all the instance samples to lie far from each other, but it only imposes a soft constraint (Eq. 4), which avoids degenerate distributions.

Note that previous work (He et al., 2020; Hénaff et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2020a) highlighted that BN may be harmful for learning semantically meaningful representations because the network can “cheat” and exploit the batch statistics in order to find a trivial solution to Eq. 2. However, our

whitening transform (Eq. 7) is applied only to the very last layer of the network $f(\cdot)$ (see Fig. 2) and it is not used in the intermediate layers, which is instead the case of BN. Hence, our $f(\cdot)$ cannot learn to exploit subtle inter-sample dependencies introduced by batch-statistics because of the lack of other learnable layers on top of the z features.

Similarly to Eq. 6, in BYOL (Grill et al., 2020) an MSE loss is used to compare the latent representations of two positives computed by slightly different networks without contrasting positives with negatives (Sec. 2). However, the MSE loss alone could be trivially minimized by a collapsed distribution, where both networks output sample-independent representations. The reason why this does not happen is still an open problem and this has opened a debate in the community (Fetterman & Albrecht, 2020; Tian et al., 2020b; Chen & He, 2020; Richemond et al., 2020). Specifically, it seems that the BN layers, included in the projection/prediction heads of BYOL are *one of the* ingredients which help to avoid degenerate solutions (Fetterman & Albrecht, 2020; Tian et al., 2020b) (see Sec. 1 and 2). Our W-MSE can be seen as a generalization of this implicit property of BYOL, in which the z values of the current batch are full-whitened, so preventing possible collapsing effects of the MSE loss. Importantly, we reach this result without the need of specific asymmetric architectures (e.g., momentum networks (Grill et al., 2020), prediction heads, etc.) or sophisticated training protocols (e.g., stop-gradient, slow-convergence of the prediction head (Chen & He, 2020), etc.).

Finally, note that using BN alone without whitening (Eq. 7), and without the aforementioned asymmetric learning, is *not sufficient*. Indeed, if we minimize the MSE after feature standardization (i.e., BN), the network can easily find a solution where, e.g., all the dimensions of the embedding represent the same feature or are correlated to each other. For instance, in preliminary experiments with CIFAR-10, we replaced whitening with BN, and the network converged to a 0 loss value after 50 epochs. Nevertheless, the linear classification accuracy was very poor: 68.15%.

Last but not least, the use of multiple positives extracted from the same image (i.e., $d > 2$) has been recently proposed in SwAV (Caron et al., 2020). However, different from our proposal, in SwAV, the multi-crop strategy is based on multiple-resolution crops, and, most importantly, in our case, we can compute $d(d-1)$ inter-positive differences in Eq. 6 with only d forward passes, while, in SwAV, the number of comparisons grows linearly with d .

4. Experiments

In our experiments we use the following **datasets**.

- CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100 (Krizhevsky & Hinton,

2009), two small-scale datasets composed of 32×32 images with 10 and 100 classes, respectively.

- ImageNet (Deng et al., 2009), the well-known large-scale dataset with about 1.3M training images and 50K test images, spanning over 1000 classes.
- Tiny ImageNet (Le & Yang, 2015), a reduced version of ImageNet, composed of 200 classes with images scaled down to 64×64 . The total number of images is: 100K (training) and 10K (testing).
- ImageNet-100 (Tian et al., 2020a), a random 100-class subset of ImageNet.
- STL-10 (Coates et al., 2011), also derived from ImageNet, with 96×96 resolution images and more than 100K training samples.

Setting. The goal of our experiments is to compare W-MSE with state-of-the-art SSL losses, isolating the effects of other settings, such as the architectural choices. For this reason, in the small and medium size dataset experiments of Tab. 1, we use the same encoder $E(\cdot)$, ResNet-18, for all the compared methods and, similarly, we use ResNet-50 for the ImageNet-based experiments in Tab. 3. When we do not report previously published results, we independently select the best hyperparameter values for each method and each dataset. In each method, the latent-space features are L_2 normalized, unless otherwise specified. In Tab. 1, *SimCLR (our repro.)* refers to our implementation of the contrastive loss (Eq. 2) following the details in (Chen et al., 2020a), with temperature $\tau = 0.5$. In the same table, *BYOL (our repro.)* is our reproduction of (Grill et al., 2020). For this method we use the exponential moving average with cosine increasing, starting from 0.99. *W-MSE 2* and *W-MSE 4* correspond to our method with $d = 2$ and $d = 4$ positives extracted per image, respectively. For CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100, the slicing sub-batch size is 128, for Tiny ImageNet and STL-10, it is 256. In the Tiny ImageNet and STL-10 experiments with W-MSE 2, we use 4 iterations of batch slicing, while in all the other experiments we use only 1 iteration.

Implementation details. For the small and medium size datasets, we use the Adam optimizer (Kingma & Ba, 2014). For all the compared methods (including ours), we use the same number of epochs and the same learning rate schedule. Specifically, for CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100, we use 1,000 epochs with learning rate 3×10^{-3} ; for Tiny ImageNet, 1,000 epochs with learning rate 2×10^{-3} ; for STL-10, 2,000 epochs with learning rate 2×10^{-3} . We use learning rate warm-up for the first 500 iterations of the optimizer, and a 0.2 learning rate drop 50 and 25 epochs before the end. We use a mini-batch size of $K = 1024$ samples. The dimension of the hidden layer of the projection head $g(\cdot)$ is 1024. The

weight decay is 10^{-6} . Finally, we use an embedding size of 64 for CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100, and an embedding of size of 128 for STL-10 and Tiny ImageNet. For ImageNet-100 we use a configuration similar to the Tiny ImageNet experiments, and 240 epochs of training. Finally, in the ImageNet experiments (Tab. 3), we use the implementation and the hyperparameter configuration of (Chen et al., 2020b) (same number of layers in the projection head, etc.) based on their open-source implementation², the only difference being the learning rate and the loss function (respectively, 0.075 and the contrastive loss in (Chen et al., 2020b) vs. 0.1 and Eq. 6 in W-MSE 4).

Image transformation details. We extract crops with a random size from 0.2 to 1.0 of the original area and a random aspect ratio from $3/4$ to $4/3$ of the original aspect ratio, which is a commonly used data-augmentation technique (Chen et al., 2020a). We also apply horizontal mirroring with probability 0.5. Finally, we apply color jittering with configuration (0.4, 0.4, 0.4, 0.1) with probability 0.8 and grayscaling with probability 0.1. For ImageNet and ImageNet-100, we follow the details in (Chen et al., 2020a): crop size from 0.08 to 1.0, stronger jittering (0.8, 0.8, 0.8, 0.2), grayscaling probability 0.2, and Gaussian blurring with 0.5 probability. In all the experiments, at testing time we use only one crop (standard protocol).

Evaluation protocol. The most common evaluation protocol for unsupervised feature learning is based on *freezing* the network encoder ($E(\cdot)$, in our case) after unsupervised pre-training, and then train a supervised *linear classifier* on top of it. Specifically, the linear classifier is a fully-connected layer followed by softmax, which is plugged on top of $E(\cdot)$ after removing the projection head $g(\cdot)$. In all the experiments, we train the linear classifier for 500 epochs using the Adam optimizer and the labeled training set of each specific dataset, without data augmentation. The learning rate is exponentially decayed from 10^{-2} to 10^{-6} . The weight decay is 5×10^{-6} . In our experiments, we also include the accuracy of a k-nearest neighbors classifier (k-nn, $k = 5$). The advantage of using this classifier is that it does not require additional parameters and training, and it is deterministic.

4.1. Comparison with the state of the art

Tab. 1 shows the results of the experiments on small and medium size datasets. For W-MSE, 4 samples are generally better than 2. The contrastive loss performs the worst in most cases. The W-MSE 4 accuracy is the best on CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100, while BYOL leads on STL-10 and Tiny ImageNet, although the gap between the two methods is marginal. In the Supplementary Material, we plot the linear classification accuracy during training for the STL-10

²<https://github.com/google-research/simclr>

dataset. The plot shows that W-MSE 4 and BYOL have a similar performance during most of the training. However, in the first 120 epochs, BYOL significantly underperforms W-MSE 4 (e.g., the accuracy after 20 epochs: W-MSE 4, 79.98%; BYOL, 73.24%), indicating that BYOL requires a “warmup” period. On the other hand, W-MSE performs well from the beginning. This property is useful in those domains which require a rapid adaptation of the encoder, e.g., due to the change of the data distribution in continual learning or in reinforcement learning.

Tab. 2 shows the results on a larger dataset (ImageNet-100). In that table, MoCo is the contrastive-loss based method proposed in (He et al., 2020), and $\mathcal{L}_{\text{align}}$ and $\mathcal{L}_{\text{uniform}}$ are the two losses proposed in (Wang & Isola, 2020) (Sec. 1-2). Note that, while W-MSE (2 and 4) in Tab. 2 refer to our method with a *ResNet-18* encoder, the other results are reported from (Wang & Isola, 2020), where a much larger-capacity network (i.e., a *ResNet-50*) is used as the encoder. *Despite this large difference in the encoder capacity*, both versions of W-MSE significantly outperform the other two compared methods in this dataset. Tab. 2 also shows that W-MSE 2, the version of our method without multi-cropping, is highly competitive, being its classification accuracy significantly higher than state-of-the-art methods.

Finally, in Tab. 3 we show the ImageNet results using 100 and 400 training epochs, and we compare W-MSE 4 with the results of other state-of-the-art approaches as reported in (Chen & He, 2020). Despite some configuration details are different (e.g., the depth of the projection head, etc.), in all cases the encoder is a ResNet-50. However, SwAV refers to the reproduction of (Caron et al., 2020) used in (Chen & He, 2020), where no multi-crop strategy is adopted (hence, $d = 2$), and a multi-crop version of SwAV may likely obtain significantly larger values. Tab. 3 shows that W-MSE 4 is the state of the art with 100 epochs and it is very close to the 400-epochs state of the art. These results confirm that our method is highly competitive, considering that we have not intensively tuned our hyperparameters and that our network is much simpler than other approaches.

4.2. Contrastive loss with whitening

In this section, we analyse the effect of the whitening transform in combination with the contrastive loss. Specifically, we use the contrastive loss (Eq. 2) on whitened features $\mathbf{z} = \text{Whitening}(\mathbf{v})$ (Eq. 7). Tab. 4 shows the results on CIFAR-10. The first row refers to the standard contrastive loss without whitening. Note that the difference with respect to Tab.1 is due to the use of only 200 training epochs. The second row refers to Eq. 2, where the features (\mathbf{z}) are computed using Eq. 7 and then L_2 normalized, while in the last two rows, \mathbf{z} is not normalized. If the features are whitened and then normalized, we observed an unstable

Table 1. Classification accuracy (top 1) of a linear classifier and a 5-nearest neighbors classifier for different loss functions and datasets with a ResNet-18 encoder.

Method	CIFAR-10		CIFAR-100		STL-10		Tiny ImageNet	
	linear	5-nn	linear	5-nn	linear	5-nn	linear	5-nn
SimCLR (Chen et al., 2020a) (our repro.)	91.80	88.42	66.83	56.56	90.51	85.68	48.84	32.86
BYOL (Grill et al., 2020) (our repro.)	91.73	89.45	66.60	56.82	91.99	88.64	51.00	36.24
W-MSE 2 (ours)	91.55	89.69	66.10	56.69	90.36	87.10	48.20	34.16
W-MSE 4 (ours)	91.99	89.87	67.64	56.45	91.75	88.59	49.22	35.44

Table 2. Classification accuracy on ImageNet-100. Top 1 and 5 correspond to the accuracy of a linear classifier. W-MSE (2 and 4) are based on a ResNet-18 encoder. † indicates that the results are based on a ResNet-50 encoder and the values are reported from (Wang & Isola, 2020).

Method	top 1	top 5	5-nn
MoCo (He et al., 2020) †	72.80	91.64	-
$\mathcal{L}_{\text{align}}$ and $\mathcal{L}_{\text{uniform}}$ (Wang & Isola, 2020) †	74.60	92.74	-
W-MSE 2 (ours)	76.00	93.14	67.04
W-MSE 4 (ours)	79.02	94.46	71.32

training, with divergence after a few epochs. The unnormalized version with whitening converged, but its accuracy is worse than the standard contrastive loss (both normalized and unnormalized).

These experiments show that the whitening transform alone does not improve the SSL performance, and, used jointly with negative contrasting, it may be harmful. Conversely, we use whitening in our W-MSE to avoid a collapsed representation (Eq. 4) when only positives are used (Eq. 3).

5. Conclusion

In this paper we proposed a new SSL loss, W-MSE, which is alternative to common loss functions used in the field. Differently from the triplet loss and the contrastive loss, both of which are based on comparing a pair of positive instances against other samples, W-MSE computes only the inter-positive distances, while using a whitening transform to avoid degenerate solutions. Our proposal is similar to recent SSL methods like BYOL (Grill et al., 2020) and SimSiam (Chen & He, 2020), which use only positives to reduce the dependence on large batch sizes (Chen et al., 2020a). However, differently from BYOL and SimSiam, which adopt asymmetric network architectures and training protocols, our solution to avoid collapsed representations is much sim-

Table 3. Classification accuracy (top 1) of a linear classifier on ImageNet with a ResNet-50 encoder. All results but ours are reported from (Chen & He, 2020). † The reproduction of SwAV in (Chen & He, 2020) does not include a multi-crop strategy.

Method	100 epochs	400 epochs
SimCLR (Chen et al., 2020a)	66.5	69.8
MoCo v2 (Chen et al., 2020c)	67.4	71.0
BYOL (Grill et al., 2020)	66.5	73.2
SwAV (Caron et al., 2020) †	66.5	70.7
SimSiam (Chen & He, 2020)	68.1	70.8
W-MSE 4 (ours)	69.43	72.56

Table 4. CIFAR-10: accuracy of the contrastive loss with whitened features, trained for 200 epochs.

Whitened features	L_2 normalized	linear	5-nn
✗	✓	89.66	86.55
✓	✓	diverged	
✗	✗	79.48	76.60
✓	✗	77.39	74.14

pler, while achieving a classification accuracy which is, in most cases, comparable or superior to the state-of-the-art methods. Despite asymmetry in learning and whitening are alternative solutions, a combination is possible. This may be a direction of future investigation.

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